

PHILOLOGY

THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN CLIL (CONTENT AND LANGUAGE INTEGRATED LEARNING) AND TRADITIONAL LEARNING

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Abstract

CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) is the teaching of exact science or technical subjects in a foreign, targeted language. This is the most common and popular foreign language teaching method. The key principles of the approach of subject-language integrated learning are based on two main concepts - "language" and "integration". With the traditional approach of teaching a foreign language, as known, much attention is paid to teaching the grammatical, lexical and phonetic components of the language. A large place is occupied by the performance of exercises of a non-communicative nature - exercises for transformation, substitution of language units and anything of this nature.

Keywords: traditional learning, integration, subject-language.

Introduction

The difference with the CLIL technology and traditional language learning method is in the CLIL the particular subject such as physics, mathematics, chemistry, biology, etc., would be chosen to be taught in English language, and in the traditional language learning method target language would be taught with every aspect of life. There are a lot of traditional methods of learning the language. Content and language integrated learning is popular nowadays, because it is killing two birds with one stone, hence it is a time saving method.

CLIL method

The acronym CLIL was created in 1994 by David Marsh, one of the researchers working in the field of multilingual and bilingual education at the University of Finland Jyväskylä. CLIL is an integrated learning method in which the language being studied and the subject to be mastered go hand in hand. This method is very successfully used in European countries. In Kazakhstan, the use of trilingualism began with the Order "On the pilot project "Roadmap for the Development of Trilingual Education" [1]. The successful application of CLIL gives us grounds to believe that this method is quite potential. One of the advantages of this method is that it has no limits in improving language skills and subject knowledge. This method also helps to use other learning strategies, apply innovative teaching methods and technologies, and increases students' motivation to study subjects and a foreign language. In addition to the advantages already listed, CLIL makes it possible to strengthen the teaching of a foreign language without requiring additional hours in the curriculum.

There is one problem in CLIL: what is more effective, to train a subject teacher in a foreign language or to teach a foreign language teacher a subject. But both of these methods require time and financial costs. Then it is more productive to teach lessons in CLIL jointly by a foreign language teacher and a subject teacher. The next problem is the choice of so-called teacher pairs. And the most effective cooperation is the joint work of teachers who are really interested in strengthening a foreign language [3].

Traditional methods of teaching foreign languages

The list of traditional language learning methods as follows:

1. Grammar-translation method
2. Natural method
3. Direct teaching method
4. Indirect methods.
5. Audio-lingual method.
6. Audio-visual method
7. Consciously-comparative method
8. Communicative method of learning a foreign language

Explanations of some methods:

Grammar-translation method. According to this method, language proficiency is grammar and vocabulary. The process of improvement is understood as a movement from one grammatical scheme to another. Thus, a teacher planning a course on this method first thinks about what grammar schemes he wants to cover. Then, texts are selected for these topics, from which individual sentences are singled out, and everything ends with a translation. First – from a foreign language to the native, then – vice versa. As for the text, it is usually the so-called artificial text, in which practically no meaning is given to the meaning: it is not so important what you say, it is important how you say it. Some adherents of this method (G. Ollendorf) believed that the texts of the textbook should be chosen so that their content repels rather than attracts students, because, when learning a language, it is important to learn grammar, and not the text, which serves only as an illustration of it [4].

Natural method. The essence of the natural method was to create the same conditions and apply the same method when teaching a foreign language as in the natural assimilation of the native language by a child. Hence the name of the method: natural. The most prominent representatives of this method were M. Berlitz, F. Gouin, M. Walter, and others. The most popular among them is M. Berlitz, whose courses and textbooks were distributed in Europe and the USA. The main goal of learning with the natural method is to

teach students to speak a foreign language. Proponents of this method proceeded from the premise that, having learned to speak, students can read and write in the target language, even without being taught the technique of reading and writing [4].

Audio-lingual method. The audio-lingual method of Ch. Friz, R. Lado is based on the behavioral approach to learning and the structural direction in linguistics. The essence of the method is that the language is treated as a “behavior” that should be taught. In accordance with this method, the language should be presented in the form of units, small in volume and graded in difficulty, structures that students master by repeating, substituting, transforming, etc. As the ultimate goal of education, a comprehensive mastery of a foreign language is put forward, i.e. all types of oral and written communication [6].

Materials and types of research

The purpose of the study to teach mathematics effectively while it will be carried out in students’ non-native language [5]. The subject content, which is mathematics, in CLIL technology is more important than the language content, however to explain the terms and formulas teacher should have a proficiency level. As a result without understanding the mathematical language in English a lesson would be difficult. And on the other hand traditional language learning is going to be less demanding, the reason of that the students will only be focused on one task which is learning the language.

The subject teacher determines the subject and language goals when planning the lesson. When defining language goals, the subject teacher can count on the help of the language teacher [2].

Research questions

Several questions to guide the research:

1. How are the classes going to be performed?
2. Will be the difficulties to find materials for CLIL?
3. Will be the difference in results between two methods?

Participants

I had one experimental group: classes for the Traditional language learning and teaching Mathematics in English language both carried out in this group which had 27 students of group M-11, from the Mathematics Department of our university. Their English language levels are varied from Pre-Intermediate to Intermediate (A2-B1 by CEFR – Common European Framework of Reference for Languages). From here we can confidently say what have lacked the group. We chose two teachers: the first one English teacher with proficiency level (C1 by CEFR – Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) of English language, the second was Mathematics teacher.

Tools

For the Traditional language learning classes were performed in a traditional way by an English teacher. The classes with CLIL technology were carried out by both teachers to achieve good results. We have chosen

5 lessons to not strain young minds. 5 lessons for traditional English learning classes and 5 lessons for Mathematics classes in English language.

Procedure

Two teachers from different Departments of our university, which are Foreign Language and Mathematics, were chosen to work together. 5 lessons for Traditional language learning classes went smooth, without any obstacles, since there is one subject to concentrate. When it came to learning Mathematics in English, certainly there was an obstacle in the face of English language, hence their brains had to work overtime. Following, students were tested for their knowledge that they gathered in those lessons. The tests were made by both teachers.

Examples from tests:

From traditional language learning lessons:

Q2. Переведите предложение на английский язык: Утром шел снег.

A) It was snowing this morning.

B) It were snowing this morning.

C) It was snowed this morning.

From teaching mathematics in English language lessons:

Problem 2. Given the matrices

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 1 \\ -2 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, B = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 5 \end{pmatrix} \text{ and } C = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & -2 \\ 4 & 1 \end{pmatrix},$$

find the linear combination $2A - 3B + 4C$.

Solution:

$$2A - 3B + 4C = [7].$$

It was not difficult to find materials for both disciplines. Workbooks were available on the Internet and teachers used videos of their foreign colleagues.

In CLIL the weight holds the subject, in our case it is Mathematics. The difference is teaching mathematics in English language. Traditional language learning is the method that is used everywhere, and students are familiar with this method.

Research results

The lessons that were performed by both teachers were successful. They followed their syllabuses that were stated by the university. Also teachers used materials from their foreign colleagues and gave references to their work.

English language teacher performed Traditional language learning lessons by herself. The lessons went pretty ordinary. At the end of the experimental lessons students took a test, and we took the results.

For Mathematics lessons the teachers performed together. The English language level of Mathematics teacher was intermediate (B1 by CEFR – Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) and she needed help from English language teacher. Mathematics teacher created a test with the assistance of English language teacher.

Students were really active throughout all the lessons. The gap in their knowledge of English language they filled with enthusiasm of pure excitement. The results we will give in a graph below.

Students achieved good results in a Traditional language learning lessons. The average result from test was 90%. The lessons where Mathematics taught in English have got a lesser result, but it was expected. Even though their results in English language lessons were good, they need to work on their Mathematics vocabulary. Overall, the results are very good.

Conclusion

The difference between Traditional language learning and CLIL is the subject matter. Students in general need to concentrate in one subject throughout a lesson. But in CLIL there are subject and a language that students have to keep in mind. They learn the subject, in our case Mathematics, and a targeted language which is English language. For majority of students it can be difficult if they are not familiar with the language. There is a huge responsibility in teachers' shoulders. Our teachers did a good job.

Teachers need to work on teaching English language with an academic direction, i.e. it is needed to include professional Mathematic terms and teachers should explain the formulas correctly. If students set to study abroad, their vocabulary should include more academic words since they ought to understand the tasks correctly.

The CLIL method is commonly used in private schools. But in State schools it is needed to create poly-

language group. And everything that needed for these type of groups. It is time consuming and can cost a lot. Hence, if we fancy creating those groups, we need to start little by little.

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